

Research

A Study on recruitment and selection process of Lithe group, Dhaka, Bangladesh

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Accepted: 01 November, 2020; Online: 06 November, 2020

DOI : <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4255193>

Abstract: *Lithe Group inaugurated its operation in 1993. Keeping its corporate mission in view, the group has over the years diversified its activities. Today this group is one of the largest Garments in Bangladesh. Lithe Group have total 7000 employees. Their Turnover \$ 60 Million and 40 Million Pcs per Months. Their main product is T-shirt, Polo shirt, Tang tops, Sweat shirt, Trousers, Jump sweats, Rompers, Sleep wear and so on. It is well admitted that people form an integral part of the organization. The efficiency and quality of its people determines the fate of the organization. Hence choosing the right people, placing them at right place and selecting those at the right time have been essentially essential. Hiring comes at this point of time in the picture. Hiring is a strategic function for HR department. Recruitment and selection form the process of hiring the employees. Recruitment is the systematic process of generating a pool of qualified applicant for organization job. The process includes the step like HR planning attracting applicant and screening them.*

This step is affected by various factors, which can be internal as well as external. The organization makes use of various methods and sources for this purpose. Different organizations adopt different approaches and techniques for their employees. To know the practical application of the employees' hiring process, the analysis of Lithe Group has been undertaken. In the later part of the study, we will have a little touch about the Lithe Group.

Keywords: *Recruitment, Training and development, performance appraisal, and reward management.*

Introduction

Lithe Group inaugurated its operation in 1993. Keeping its corporate mission in view, the group has over the years diversified its activities. Today this group is one of the largest Garments in

Bangladesh. Lithe Group have total 7000 employees. Their Turnover \$ 60 Million and 40 Million Pcs per Months. Their main product is T-shirt, Polo shirt, Tang tops, Sweat shirt, Trousers, Jump sweats, Rompers, Sleep wear and so on.

The business world is getting dynamic and competitive. It is hard for an organization to run & even survive in a fast paced, growing and uncertain world if it cannot keep tracks with the go of business dynamism. Business plays and links important roles in developing the economy of a country. So, as a business graduate, I think I need to be attached with any organization to get a handy & versatile experience about the business world & HR issues that will in my career.

Dissertation is the arrangement, which makes a bridge between our academic knowledge and practical world to have an acquaintance with the real business world as well as to gear me up to lead the future competitive business. I have worked in HR & Admin Department of Lithe Group, head office. In this report, I will try to make an overall analysis on “Recruitment & Selection Process” of Lithe Group.³ Objectives of the Study

Broad Objective:

The broad objective of this study is to evaluate the recruitment and selection process of Lithe Group.

Specific Objective:

To explore the recruitment and selection process of the Lithe Group.

To find out the problems of recruitment and selection practices.

It is well admitted that people form an integral part of the organization. The efficiency and quality of its people determines the fate of the organization. Hence choosing the right people, placing them at right place and selecting those at the right time have been essentially essential. Hiring comes at this point of time in the picture. Hiring is a strategic function for HR department. Recruitment and selection form the process of hiring the employees. Recruitment is the systematic process of generating a pool of qualified applicant for organization job. The process includes the step like HR planning attracting applicant and screening them. This step is affected by various factors, which can be internal as well as external. The organization makes use of various methods and sources for this purpose. Different organizations adopt different approaches and techniques for their employees. To know the practical application of the employees’ hiring

process, the analysis of Lithe Group has been undertaken. In the later part of the study, we will have a little touch about the Lithe Group.

Materials and methods

1. Lecture Review:

The notion of what Recruitment and Selection is, and how it should be done has constantly changed over the past number of years- From Smith and Robertson (1986) to Woodruffe (1993) to O'Reilly and Pfeffer (2000) to Pilbeam and Corbridge (2006) to the most up to date in Taylor (2010), Armstrong (2010) and Gunnigle (2011)- lots of different people have weighed in with their opinions on how organizations can improve their recruitment and selection methods. The idea of recruitment and selection was once just to fill the vacant position as soon as possible and forget about it again but this has changed dramatically- with hundreds of people exploring this area in the hope to find the perfect method. The object of this chapter is to review the literature on recruitment and selection- looking at the wastage or labour turnover organizations can typically expect, the job analysis or designs which may need to be conducted or drawn up, to the competitive advantage a company can obtain, to the processes they can use to recruit and select employees. It will then look at the different recruitment and selection processes the Manufacturing Company could use, be it the classic trio, work samples or even assessment centres. Finally it will look at the theories on exit interviews, and how organizations can use them to improve their business.

2.1 Human Resource Management (HRM or HR):

Human resource management is the strategic approach to the effective management of people in a company or organization such that they help their business gain a competitive advantage. It is designed to maximize employee performance in service of an employer's strategic objectives. Human resource management is primarily concerned with the management of people within organizations, focusing on policies and systems. HR departments are responsible for overseeing employee-benefits design, employee recruitment, training and development, performance appraisal, and reward management, such as managing pay and benefit systems. HR also concerns itself with organizational change and industrial relations, or the balancing of organizational practices with requirements arising from collective bargaining and governmental laws.

The overall purpose of human resources (HR) is to ensure that the organization is able to achieve success through people. HR professionals manage the human capital of an organization and focus on implementing policies and processes. They can specialize in finding, recruiting, training, and developing employees, as well as maintaining employee relations or benefits. Training and development professionals ensure that employees are trained and have continuous development. This is done through training programs, performance evaluations, and reward programs. Employee relations deals with the concerns of employees when policies are broken, such as cases involving harassment or discrimination. Managing employee benefits includes developing compensation structures, parental leave programs, discounts, and other benefits for employees. On the other side of the field are HR generalists or business partners. These HR professionals could work in all areas or be labor relations representatives working with unionized employees.

HR is a product of the human relations movement of the early 20th Century, when researchers began documenting ways of creating business value through the strategic management of the workforce. It was initially dominated by transactional work, such as payroll and benefits administration, but due to globalization, company consolidation, technological advances, and further research, HR as of 2015 focuses on strategic initiatives like mergers and acquisitions, talent management, succession planning, industrial and labor relations, and diversity and inclusion. In the current global work environment, most companies focus on lowering employee turnover and on retaining the talent and knowledge held by their workforce. New hiring not only entails a high cost but also increases the risk of a new employee not being able to adequately replace the position of the previous employee. HR departments strive to offer benefits that will appeal to workers, thus reducing the risk of losing employee commitment and psychological ownership.

2.2 Recruitment:

In human resource management, “recruitment” is the process of finding and hiring the best and most qualified candidate for a job opening, in a timely and cost-effective manner. It can also be defined as the “process of searching for prospective employees and stimulating and encouraging them to apply for jobs in an organization”.

It is one whole process, with a full life cycle, that begins with identification of the needs of the company with respect to the job, and ends with the introduction of the employee to the organization.

2.3 Recruitment and Selection:

Recruitment and selection methods have changed and opinions have evolved over the course of time. It was once the policy to fill the position as quickly as possible but as time has progressed organizations have realized that the recruitment and selection methods they employ can have serious effects on how the organization operates, and thus the turnover the organization makes. “Attracting and recruiting the best employees is critical to success in all sectors and to all types of organizations, regardless of size” (Cullen & Farrelly, 2005, p. 41). Froschheiser (2008) has claimed that putting the wrong person into the wrong position just to fill it can have dire consequences to your organization, it may cause poor employee morale, low productivity and lost opportunities- all of which will have a negative impact on your organizations bottom line. As a result of this there is increasing pressure on organizations to ensure that they implement the best recruitment and selection method applicable to their organization or industry otherwise they risk becoming uncompetitive.

Turner (2010) backs this up with this when he claims that the success of any organization depends on its ability to get the right people, in the right place at the right time. 13 Many authors who have studied recruitment and selection have agreed that there is a distinct difference between recruitment and selection. Taylor (2008) and Rees and French (2010) say that recruitment is the process whereby an organization collects applications for a position and generates a pool of potential suitable employees, while selection involves using techniques or different methods to assess the applicants and decide who is best suited to the available position, given management goals and legal requirements.

2.4 Recruitment Process:

Recruitment is a process of finding and attracting the potential resources for filling up the vacant positions in an organization. It sources the candidates with the abilities and attitude, which are required for achieving the objectives of an organization.

Recruitment process is a process of identifying the jobs vacancy, analyzing the job requirements, reviewing applications, screening, shortlisting and selecting the right candidate.

To increase the efficiency of hiring, it is recommended that the HR team of an organization follows the five best practices (as shown in the following image). These five practices ensure successful recruitment without any interruptions. In addition, these practices also ensure consistency and compliance in the recruitment process.

Recruitment process is the first step in creating a powerful resource base. The process undergoes a systematic procedure starting from sourcing the resources to arranging and conducting interviews and finally selecting the right candidates.

Fig: Recruitment Process

3. Methodology of the study

To undergo this study, I have followed a set of methodologies. These are given below. In the organization part, much of the information has been collected from different published articles, journals, brochures, web-sites and so on.

3.1 Research Philosophy and Approach:

The research philosophy applied by any researcher is very important as should the wrong philosophy be applied it may impact the researchers overall findings thus labelling the findings unreliable or invalid and rendering the research as null and void. There are a number of issues which researchers must consider before choosing their method for data collection and analysis. Saunders et al, (2009) developed a research “onion”- a multi-layered diagram where they suggest

researchers must start on the outside and peel through each layer to make sure they get the most appropriate research strategy, design and methodology. (Saunders, et al., 2009) 35 Research philosophy is concerned with the development of knowledge- how it has been developed and what assumptions researchers have made or can make about it. These assumptions will depend on whether the researcher takes an ontological or epistemological viewpoint. Ontology deals with the nature of reality and whether a researcher subscribes to objectivism or subjectivism. Epistemology concerns itself with what constitutes as acceptable knowledge, and this will depend on whether the researcher adopts a positivist or interpretivist stance- that is, whether a person is to rely on facts or impressions. Whichever philosophical stance the researcher adopts will determine the research approach, which in the case of positivism will be deductive and in the case of interpretivism will be inductive, however, it is also common to combine both approaches. Saunders et al, (2009), are quick to point out that no research philosophy is better than another- research questions will often fall into more than one domain, so therefore adopting one over another is not totally practical in reality. They conclude by describing the pragmatist philosophy, where they say- the most important thing a researcher must consider when applying a research strategy and methodology is research question(s).

3.2 Analysis of the Recruitment and Selection Process 1361

“necessary competence”; (3) How the selection processes encompass the assumptions and commitments, the generalities, truths and confusions—of decision-makers about the imperatives of organization culture and how they seek to maintain and change this.

Selection activities typically follow a standard pattern, beginning with an initial screening interview and concluding with the final employment decision. The selection process may consist of following steps:

- (1) Initial screening interview;
- (2) Completing the application form;
- (3) Comprehensive interview;
- (4) Background investigation;
- (5) Medical/Physical examination;
- (6) Final job offer.

Each of these steps represents a decision point requiring some affirmative feedback for the process to continue. Each step in the process seeks to expand the organization's knowledge about the applicant's background, abilities, motivation, and it increases the information from which decision makers make their predictions and final choice. However, some steps may be omitted if they do not yield data that aids in predicting success, or if the cost of the step is not warranted.

3.3 Orientation

According to Whiddett et al. [12], Orientation is the introduction of new employees to the organization, their work units, and their jobs. Employees receive orientation from their co workers and from the organization. An effective orientation program has an immediate and lasting impact on the new employee and can make the difference between his or her success and failure.

3.4 Employee Development

According to an article by Barnerjee [1], employee development, in sharp contrast to training, is more future oriented and more concerned with education than employee training. Development focuses on planting a sound reasoning process in employees. It enhances their ability to understand and interpret knowledge rather than imparting a body of facts or teaching a set of skills. A development path for an employee, imparts in him analytical, human, conceptual and specialized skills. It makes him able to think and analyze in different situations. Development, therefore, focuses more on the employee's personal growth. It is important to consider one critical component of employee development: All employees, at no matter what level, can be developed.

(Saunders, et al., 2009)

3.5 Performance Appraisal

According to Murad [7] “Performance appraisal is the process of determining and communicating to an employee how he or she is performing on the job and, ideally, establishing a plan of improvement”. When properly conducted, performance appraisals not only let employees know how well they are performing but also influence their future level of effort and task direction. Effort should be enhanced if the employee is properly reinforced. The task perception of the employee should be clarified through the establishment of a proper plan for improvement.

An analysis of HRM requires that some kind of a conceptual framework, general one be defined, to better understand the complexity of such a context. HRM practices in companies can thus be seen as an amalgamation of foreign methods and techniques rather than specifically developed tools. This is once an example of the positive and negative aspects of the country’s pragmatism. The personnel function must be analyzed both via its activities and the various structures within it work.

The personnel function has changed over the years and has followed a certain “chronology” which can be accounted for by outside constraints affecting a company and by inner conflicts which management has to resolve. Finally as well as the diversity of situations affecting companies, the “limited rationale” of the agents (employers, managers, personnel, unions) and the diversity of their respective strategies must also be considered. Having in mind the above

mentioned aspects and the fact that the companies also tend to react strongly to current managerial practice and ideas, several phases in personnel function may be following; Personnel Administration: The formalization of personnel administration is closely linked to the widespread development of the scientific organization of work.

Personnel manager's initiatives were limited to social benefits (pensions, sick benefits) and the correct management of social institutions.

Management of Human Resources: Economic growth and increased competition combined with the troublesome development of dysfunctional behaviour (absenteeism, staff turnover, sabotage, vandalism) in large industrial and administrative concerns made employers look for new concepts in management.

Organizational Management: The past ten years have been characterized by a growing number of interactions between the company and other groups (competitors, financiers, customers) and by dual need for flexibility and quality, the somewhat contradictory role. It is essential that management master the internal interaction among the various members of the organization.

To develop/establish a research on an understanding that those individuals who are recruited or selected through the traditional and new methods are fit for the organization and the analysis of the HRM team who undertake this responsibility of fulfilling this task. The main idea of research is the analysis of the organizations gain's and loss on the finance used for the recruiting and selection of the persons and what have the outcome been there for the organization. The aim of the research is to find out the main drawbacks in the Recruiting and Selection processes involved in the HRM department in any organization. The research conducted by me on this topic was quite interesting and

I did come across a very vast area of these processes and tried to figure out how to

According to Biz Mag [6] businesses have to plan carefully to ensure they have the right number of employees for their needs. To do this they need a good understanding of the labour market and have the full use of Human Resources. Human Resources planning also involves looking at how labour or workforce is organized within the company or business.

3.6 Variable Covered:

This is descriptive types of research, which briefly discuss the recruitment and selection procedure of Lithe Group. It has been administered by collection both primary and secondary data. 3.7 Sampling Design:

Population: The target population was the employees who in Lithe Group. **Sample Size:** The sample size was 30 respondents which include both executive and operative employees.

3.8 Sample Techniques

Random sampling will be used as sampling technique to select the respondent for this study because the population will have equal opportunity for being selected as respondents. The purposive sampling (e.g. non-probability sampling technique) technique will be used to select respondents who are directly connected with the recruitment and selection process from the HR department.

3.9 Methods of Collecting Data:

The Non-Probability Convenience sampling method was used for the collection of information and to identify the respondents.

Data Sources: All the information incorporated in this report have been collected both from the primary sources and as well as from the secondary sources.

Primary Sources of Data:

Several approaches are available for getting primary data. To collect the valid and reliable data questionnaire has sent to the employees of the Lithe Group and responses are recorded.

Secondary Sources of Data:

To collect the data for conducting the study secondary sources has been be used as well. It includes books, internet, articles, and journals. This will help to assess other's sources of data, defined and measured the concept and how this study is related with other studies.

Population:

Lithe Group has been selected for the study. The population of the study will be consisted of employees from different companies of Lithe Group.

Data Collection Methods:

Primary source of information:

- Discussion with officials of the company
- Desk work
- Observation
- Secondary source of data
- Annual report of the company
- Relevant papers and published documents of Lithe Group
- Published books, articles, journals, magazines and so on

3.11 Data Analysis:

For the analysis of data, I have used the followings: -

- Tables
- Figures
- Charts/ Graphical representations;
- Microsoft word
- Microsoft excels
- Micro soft Visio

Questionnaires:

To identify and assess the effectiveness of the Recruitment and Selection of Lithe Group questionnaire has been used. A set of questionnaires have been prepared with open and close ended questions. And this questionnaire I have been used the Likert Scale process only for close ended question.

Various kinds of rating scales have been developed to measure attitudes directly (i.e. the person knows their attitude is being studied). The most widely used is the Likert scale (1932).

In its final form, the Likert scale is five or seven types of scale which is used to allow the individual to express how much they agree or disagree with a particular statement. But in my report I just use five types of likert scale. These five (05) are.....

- Strongly Disagree

- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly Agree

3.12 Importance and Scope

1. This project will provide a value insight to student on the topic.
2. This project will help to get the practical knowledge in employee hiring in the organization.

4. Lithe Group recruitment and selection policy

An effective recruitment and selection process require a well set of recruitment and selection policies. As a big organization, Lithe Group also has a distinctive set of policies. Recruitment and selection policies are simple. But the implication of these policies can be far reaching and far-sighted.

Lithe Group recruitment and selection policies are given below:

- Lithe Group recruitment policy is to hire the right kind of people at the right place, selecting them through an effective process from a pool of candidates in the job market.
- Lithe Group recruitment and selection policy does not allow any favor or preferential treatment to anyone.
- Any person who has contract with any other company cannot be hired under any type of contract.
- The recruitment and selection department of Lithe Group has the freedom from all political and other pressures.
- Anyone who is under 18 years of age cannot be hired as an employee under regular, temporary and part-time contract.

- The status of employment can be changed from contract to regular and regular to contract depending on the situations arising from performance or need.
- The competency and high-quality performance of the whole organization shall be ensured by the effective recruitment and selection.
- Lithe Group follows the above policies in the time of human resource planning and recruiting new employees.

4.1 Recruitment sources:

There are two sources from which recruitment is facilitated. Recruitment may be either from the internal source that is within the organization or from the external job market.

4.2 Internal source:

Internal source is a very important source. For encouraging the internal candidates, job vacancies in the Lithe Group are advertised through internal notices to all company employees. Recruitment from the internal source is done through promotion or delegating individuals with new assignments.

In the case of internal sourcing, HR along with concerned Division or Department will identify prospective candidates on the basis of individual capability matching with Competency/Role profile and will conduct appropriate tests to select the most suited person.

The process of internal sourcing

- **Vacancy Found:** When a vacancy is found in a particular position, the first thing that the HR does is that they look for an appropriate person to fill in the vacancy.
- **Matching Capabilities:** Later, the HR department seeks for matching the capabilities the targeted person has and the post requires.
- **Offering the Person:** Next, the targeted person is called at a meeting to discuss comprehensively whether he is ready or not. If he is found enthusiastic, he is offered the post in form of promotion.

- **Placing:** In this stage, the person is placed with the appropriate job description of the post he is going to hold.

4.3 External sources:

In addition to looking internally for candidates, organizations mostly open up recruiting efforts to the external community. In Lithe Group recruitment from external sources undergoes the following process-

- **Executive search:** Executive search firms are used for searching senior managers and higher positions.
- **Web sites:** The Company tends to use its web site as an external source of recruitment. In this site, an application form is provided for the interested candidates to fill in. When the organization needs to fill in some vacancies, the HR officers log on to here and sort some CVs and contact the qualified the people.
- **Advertisements:** Advertisements in the national daily and jobsites for managers and lower level position are published. In some cases, the job sites on internet are used only. It is done because the organization needs the people who are well aware of internet and outsides.
- **Words of Mouth:** Sometimes, it is seen that the HR officers are sending the mails to their familiar people within and outside the organization. They do it when they need a bunch of people within a short time. When they send the mails, they mention there that the candidates are going to be recruited on an emergency basis. So, if someone has anyone interested to do the proposed job, he or she can let the candidates contact the HR.
- **Job Fair:** Lithe Group also recruits people sometimes from job fairs held in different universities or places. It is well recognized that this group is the biggest recruiter in the job fair.

4.4 The Selection Activities:

The selection activities begin after the requisition is given by the heads of different division and advertisements are published announcing a vacancy in the organization. In the recruitment Cycle, the rest of the 27 days go in selection activities. That means after deducting 7 days for requisition and 10 days for advertisement from 10 days. Selection activities follow a standard pattern.

8.3

Recruitment Requisitions:

For these requisitions advertisement are given in the daily newspaper and bd jobs, which is a popular jobsite. Applications are submitted in the HR Department are collected and scrutinized. The applications then short listed.

Requisition by the divisional heads must contain job description and requirement. According to these description and requirement HR prepared advertisement. As discussed curlier for executive position candidate must be at least master’s degree, for executive and above level, candidate must have at least 2nd class in all academic level etc.

Questionnaire Analysis

1. What types of sources are used for recruitment in the Your organization?

Interpretation:

The above figure shows that 50% respondents' external sources, 50% respondent' internal sources are used for recruitment in Lithe Group.

Comments: Lithe Group uses both internal & external sources to recruitment employees.

2. Which internal sources are used in your organization?

Interpretation:

The above figure shows that 60% promotion, 40% transfer, are used for internal recruitment in Lithe Group

Comments: Lithe Group uses promotion, transfer and demotion sources in the internal recruitment

3. Which external sources are used in the organization for recruitment?

Interpretation:

The above figure shows that Lithe Group uses external sources for 55% advertisement, 25% walks-ins, 0% head-hunting and 20% via internet for recruitment.

■ Head- hunting

Comments: Lithe Group uses advertisement, walks-in-interview and internet for regular and executive staff

4. What types of test is used for selecting an employee in Lithe Group?

Interpretation:

The above figure shows that all respondents answered, Lithe Group uses 50% written test and 50% viva of selecting an employee.

Comments: Lithe Group use both written and viva test of selecting an employee.

5. Recruitment and Selection procedure is systematic in Lithe Group.

Interpretation:

The above figure shows that 30% strongly agree, 20% agree and 40% neutral, 10% disagree with the statement that recruitment & the selection procedure of Lithe Group.

Comment: It means that Lithe Group maintains recruitment and selection procedure systematically.

6. The tools or techniques are used for selecting an employee appropriate in Lithe Group.

Interpretation:

The above figure shows that 10% respondents strongly agreed, 40% respondents agreed, 40% respondents were neutral, and 10% respondents were disagreed about the statement.

Comments: It means used tools or techniques for selecting an employee appropriate in Lithe Group.

7. **Recruitment & Selection process by this organization is helpful for searching and selecting effective employees.**

Interpretation:

The above figure shows that 35% respondents strongly agreed, 40% respondents agreed, 20% respondents were neutral, and 5% respondents disagreed about the statement.

Comment: In Lithe Group recruitment selection process is helpful for searching and selecting effective employees.

SWOT Analysis of Recruitment and Selection Practices in Lithe Group

It is well known that SWOT analysis is the comparative study among the strength, weakness, opportunity and threats of a particular organization. The strength and the weakness refer to the internal factors of the organization and the opportunity and threats refer to the external factors of the organization. If an organization can do its SWOT analysis well, the organization doesn't tend to fall short anywhere.

Basing on the study of Lithe Group, I have tried to have a SWOT analysis on the basis of recruitment and selection practices of the group.

In the following, the whole thing understood by me is presented.

1 Strengths:

- **Good reputation:** During the study, I have found that a rush of CV is coming against a particular post. In some cases, it is found that I have received I have 100 CVs for a single post. From this perspective, it can be said that the organization has a good reputation in the job market. For this reason, the organization gets an opportunity to choose from the lots of alternatives. This is certainly strength of the organization.
- **Strong Technology:** Strength of the organization is that it has a strong technology to maintain the recruitment and selection practices. All the procedures of the organization are well maintained by technological support. This is termed as a great strength.
- **Effective Human Resource Plan:** The human resource plan is very effective and insightful. The plans are well executed and reviewed comprehensively.
- **Quality Top Management:** The top management of the organization tends to be built on quality. The top priority of the top management is one and that is quality. Even, the top management of the organization well qualified. This is very great strength of the organization.
- **Qualified Employee:** The qualified employees are a great strength of the organization. Here, at any level of administrative posts, the minimum qualification is Masters. For this reason, all the employees in the head office are university graduates.
- **Strong Team Work:** The greatest strength of the organization is that the recruitment and selection team here work in a synchronized way and in team. Their team activities are very strong.

2 Weakness:

- **Poor Looking HR Building:** The HRM building is supposed to look fantastic and colorful. But in the Lithe Group, the HRM building is not that much fashionable. For this reason, the highly ambitious candidates come to sit for the tests but after the seeing the

environment, they do not want to join here. The candidates from the foreign universities and top class public and private universities tend to do this. This is termed as a weakness.

- **Shortage of Exam Halls:** The focal weakness of this organization is that the building doesn't have good support of exam halls. When the recruitment team plans to recruit the sales representatives in larger number, they can't do it. This doesn't happen because they don't have good support of exam halls.
- **Website Is Not Updated:** The last but not the least weakness of the organization is that though the technology team is very strong here, their website is well updated as much as it should be. For this reason, the interested candidates fall short of information prior to coming here in the organization.

3 Opportunities:

- **Want of Jobs in the Public Sector:** A greater demand of jobs found due to the gaps in the public sector creates an opportunity for this company. As the population grows, the demand for jobs grows. To meet up this demand, the public sector is really unable. For the reason, Lithe Group is getting the opportunity to fill in the vacant posts with more qualified candidates.
- **Changing Mentality of the New Entrants:** The new entrants into the job market are a bit changed now. They have a tendency that the public jobs are not smart, fashionable and lucrative. To them, the public jobs are a bit like the classical old schools with little amenity of modern life. So, they move to getting the private jobs like in the Lithe Group.

4 Threats:

- **Increasing Number of Companies:** The increasing number of companies in the country poses a greater threat to the Lithe Group. As the number of companies is growing, the job market is becoming more and more open and competitive. In this backdrop, the candidates are getting a lot of options to find the jobs. So, whenever they want, they are getting the scope to switch over another job. Hence, with so many alternatives present in the job market, the company finds it really threatening to retain the best employees it has and to recruit the best candidates it can have.

- **Misconception of Candidates:** During the study, I found that many of the candidates of the candidates have a misconception about the Lithe Group. Even, this misconception is accelerated by its envious competitors. Though the group doesn't many things to do about the misconception among the candidates, it is posing a greater threat to the good will of the company.
- **Lucrative Offers of the MNCs:** The MNCs existing in the country are offering a handsome salary at the very outset. Say for example; if a well-qualified join NESTLE or GRAMEEN PHNOE, he or she is offered minimum 25000- 30000 BDT, but in this organization, the new entrant is offered 8000- 12000 BDT. The amount it offers may not be a question but when the candidates get better offers, they never tend to join here. This is supposed to create a talent gap in the organization.

5 Summary of the findings

The findings of the study are as follows:

- The recruitment and selection practices of the Lithe Group are suffering from internal and external pressures. As a result, the HRD of the Lithe Group cannot recruit and select the best candidates to fill-up the vacant position of the organization.
- The manager of the Lithe Group cannot conduct an ideal recruitment and selection program due to the existence of old and classical styles. That is why, disqualified candidates can get the chance to submit their CVs in the organization and it creates problems on the activities of HR Department.
- The HR Department of the Lithe Group always takes employee referrals for recruiting and selecting the right candidates to fill-up the vacant position of the organization. As they put a lot of importance on the referrals, they most often fail to locate the right candidates for the right job.
- The recruitment and selection policies of this organization are not well organized in some cases. For this reason, some problems always take place in the course of recruitment and selection.

- There is no waiting room for the waiting candidates in the building
- There is no central interview board in the organization.
- There is no complain box in which the outgoing candidates can give their feedback.
- The recruitment and selection policy of this company is not up-to-date.
- The recruitment policies are not updated as proactively and timely as demanded.

Conclusion

The project called “Recruitment and Selection of Lithe Group” is assigned by the organization. During developing this project, I have gathered a cargo of experiences which, I believe strongly, will be a very valuable resource in my practical life in future.

Recruiting and Selecting are a unique process of discovering potential candidates for actual and anticipated organizational vacancies. From another perspective, it is a linking activity that brings those with jobs to fill and those seeking jobs together. The success of recruiting and selecting also needs cooperation of the department in which a position is vacant. They must give the description and specification of the job for which a person will be hired. At the same time, HR also needs to analyze the nature of that job. The effective analysis will lead to an effective advertisement that will attract the qualified and discourage the disqualified.

Timely requisition is also very important; simultaneously the HR needs continuous monitoring for the upcoming vacant positions in every department. As retention of employees has become the greatest challenge of an organization, the recruiters have to be careful enough and visionary to select people so that the new entrant can be retained for a long time; fitting in the best position he or she deserves. It is a common scenario that every, large or small, multinational company controls its huge number of employees through HRD. In line with that, organizations throughout the world are quickly changing and improving the quality.

In this backdrop now-a-days, the role of HRD has become very important and to say frankly the most integral part of an organization.

The Human Resource Department of Lithe Group is strong, supportive to its employees. Concomitantly, the HRD coordinate the other department in an effective way so that the organization goals can be achieved optimally.

In fine, Lithe Group recruitment and selection effort by HRD is really ideal. This ideal recruitment and selection effort brings in a satisfactory number of qualified applicants by dint of its effectiveness and efficiency for the optimal growth of the organization. That's why; Lithe Group is enjoying and experiencing a continuous development in their pursuit of excellence.

Reference:

1. Adams, J., et al., (2007). Research methods for graduate business and social science students. New Delhi: Response Books.
2. Arhnborg S., (1997). Careers in Focus: The art of choosing new employees. Stockholm: Swedish publishers.
3. Armstrong, M., (2009). A Handbook of Human Resource Management Practice. 11th ed. London: Kogan Ltd.
4. Armstrong, M., (2006). A Handbook of Human Resource Management Practice. 10th ed. Great Britain: Cambridge University.
5. Armstrong, M., (2008). Strategic Human Resource Management. London: Kogan Ltd.
6. Bamouw, V. (1963) Culture and Personality, Homewood, IL: The Dorsey Press.
7. Bartz, A. E. (1986) Basic Statistical Concept, New York: Macmillan, Inc.
8. Beaumont, P. B. (1993) Human Resource Management: Key Concepts and Skills, London: Sage Publications.
9. Blyton, P. and Tumbull, P. (1992) Reassessing Human Resource Management, London: Sage Publications.
10. Budhwar, P. S. and Sparrow, P. R. (1997) 'Evaluating Levels of Strategic Integration and Development of Human Resource Management in India
11. Cherrington, D. J. (1995) 'Job Analysis and Strategic Recruitment', in Cherrington, D. J. (Ed.), The Management and Human Resources, Englewood Cliffs: Prentice Hall.
12. Chin, M. (1993) The Study of Satisfaction of Human Resource Management Operations in Organizations, MBA Thesis, University of Jong Shan, Taiwan

13. Conrad, P. and Pieper, R. (1990) 'Human Resource Management in the Federal Republic of Germany', in Pieper, R. (Ed.) Human Resource Management: an International Comparison
14. De Cenzo, D. A and Robbins, S. P. (1996) Human Resource Management, New York: John Wiley & Sons, Inc.
15. Dyer, L. (1984) 'Studying Human Resource Strategy: An Approach and An Agenda
16. Dyer, L. (1985) 'Strategic Human Resources Management and Planning', in Rowland, K. M. and Ferris, G. R., and Greenwich, Ct. (Ed.), Research in Personnel and Human Resources Management.
17. Dessler, G. (2007). Human Resource Management. New Delhi: Prentice Hall of India Private Limited.
18. Dessler, Gray (2017) Human Resource Management (14th edition) Pearson, India.
19. Evans, P.A. L. (1986) 'The Strategic Outcomes of Human Resource Management.
20. Filella, J. and Soler, C. (1993) 'Spain', in Brewster, C., Hegewisch, A., Lockhart, J. T., and Holden, L. (Eds.), The European Human Resource Management Guide, London: Academic Press.
21. Graham, H. T. and Bennett, R. (1995) Human Resources Management, London: Longman Group.
22. Guest, D. (1987) 'Human Resource Management and Industrial Relations', Journal of Management Studies
23. Guest, D. (1989) 'Human Resource Management: Its Implications for Industrial Relations and Trade Unions
24. Hendry, C. (1991) International Comparisons of Human Resource Management: Putting the Firm in the Frame, International Journal of Human Resource Management
25. Konings, P., (1993). Labor Resistance in Cameroon., London: James Curry Publishers.
26. Lien, D., (2002). "Rent Seeking and Allocative Efficiency: The Case of Bribery", Pacific Economic Review, 7(2002) Pg 123-133.
27. Lindelöw, M., (2008). Competence-Based Human Resource Strategy. Stockholm: Nature and Culture publishers.
28. Lowe, A., et al., (2002). Management Research: An introduction. (2nd ed). London: Sage Publications.
29. Robbins Stephen P, Coulter Mary (2018) Management (13th edition) Pearson, India.

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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